

PROSPECTS OF USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: In this scientific article, the scientific research works of foreign and our republican scientists on the introduction of innovative activities in the sustainable development of innovation, economic sectors, including agriculture, are studied.

KEY WORDS: innovation, economy, activity, research, science, production, processing.

INTRODUCTION: Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, consistent measures to ensure wider integration of science, education and production, to create and apply new knowledge, to introduce innovative technologies, best practices is being implemented. However, the results of the research on the introduction of innovative technologies and the development of the agricultural sector do not reach the lowest levels of the sector, and the problems that have not been solved for years prevent the agricultural sector from developing more rapidly. Therefore, in the future, "as one of the main directions of agricultural development, the creation of effective mechanisms for the dissemination of knowledge integrated with the production of research, education and consulting services, the development of the system of science, education, information and consulting services " is set as a priority task. This situation requires the development of scientific and methodological bases for increasing the efficiency of innovative processes in increasing the economic potential of agricultural entities, conducting systematic research on the scientific-theoretical and methodological aspects of these processes.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. According to the 30th goal of the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, to increase the income of farmers and farmers by at least 2 times, to bring the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5%, In the 141st task, supply raw materials to agro-industrial enterprises and increase the production volume by 1.5 times, including the development of a program for 2022, the volume of industrialized fruits and vegetables to 3.4 million tons, processing capacity to 3.1 million tons and to increase the processing level to 16%, to increase the capacity of fruit and vegetable processing to 3.1 million tons (107%), milk to -2.9 million tons (111.5%), meat to -410 thousand tons (119%) , increasing the assortment of food products (processed meat-milk, fruit-vegetables, oil-oil, etc.) from 898 to 1100, 3.2 thousand the tasks of creating new jobs are defined. Based on the above, it is important to increase the economic efficiency of growing fruits and vegetables in agricultural enterprises, reducing waste in the processing process. Taking into account these circumstances, increasing the added value in the process of processing fruits and vegetables in agricultural enterprises today is considered one of the urgent scientific research problems and has scientific-theoretical and practical importance. .

The currently used methods of drying agricultural products and various fruits and vegetables in the processing industry require the use of new processing technologies that increase the quality of the final product, shorten the processing time, and improve the quality of the dehydrated material. The process of dehydrating wet products using a drying agent is called drying. In this process, moisture passes from the composition of the solid phase to the gas (or steam) phase by evaporation. The use of new technologies equipped with a thermal field for drying products, a vacuum drying device with a liquid phase heat carrier, and a heat storage battery during drying processes is undoubtedly effective in the technological processes of product production.

MAIN PART. Based on the theoretical views and analyzes presented above, in our opinion, innovation is the use of scientific achievements and best practices, improvement and development processes of social production, products with new consumer characteristics (goods, products, techniques, technology, other organizational forms and tools). is the materialized final result of investment and creative activity based on formation, implementation, helps to satisfy market and social needs, saves costs and ensures that people have different results in different areas of life and activity

Foreign and domestic scientists have conducted a number of scientific studies aimed at solving the following problems: reducing energy efficiency and resource intensity during drying of agricultural products, fruits and vegetables, increasing the efficiency of dryers. creation of technologies that ensure preservation of biologically active substances during drying of fruits, vegetables and agricultural products.

In order to obtain a high yield in agriculture, it is necessary to carry out agrotechnical activities in a timely and high-quality manner. Many studies and experiments show that if agrotechnical activities are not carried out in early spring, no matter how well the soil is cut, it will dry out when the soil rises. The plan loses moisture, the fields are overrun with weeds.

The experience of developed countries shows that one of the main conditions for increasing the efficiency of agricultural production is a high level of technical equipment, the use of advanced technologies, that is, innovative activity is the basis of the economic strategy of developed countries. According to estimates, 30% of economic growth is provided by increasing labor costs, 40% by increasing labor productivity, and 30% by applying innovative technologies. Currently, Uzbekistan has all the necessary socio-economic bases for deepening innovation processes and strengthening the innovation base. However, there are problems in moving the agrarian sector to the path of innovative development, or in other words, implementing innovative projects even at the scale of one or several farms, because farms and entities processing agricultural products are currently slowness of participation in the ordering of scientific research works and funding of research, the inability of the economic entity to carry out research in the development of advanced innovative technologies and the financing of scientific research, development of agricultural products for the use of new technology, new varieties producers and processors do not have enough knowledge, they need to use the services of scientists and specialists, and farmers face certain difficulties in processing and selling products. Problems such as insufficient demand of producers for innovative developments prepared by scientists of higher educational institutions and scientific research institutions, lack of organic connection between them, irresponsibility of some producers of agricultural products hinder innovation in agriculture. can be included among the factors that hinder the processes. The development and implementation of

technical and technological innovations will be aimed at reducing the current and investment (capital) costs of production, maximum adaptation of the used techniques and technologies to the natural climate, soil and specific characteristics of each region.

CONCLUSION. The problems of innovative development are of particular importance for Uzbekistan, because only innovative development with the wide and effective use of new resource-efficient, advanced technologies will ensure rapid growth of the economy, taking into account the preservation of the environment. In the current conditions. without denying the importance of other directions in the innovative development of the agricultural sector, we consider technical and technological innovations to be the most important direction in terms of agricultural modernization.

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